

REVIEW OPEN ACCESS

Artificial Intelligence Literacy: Scientific Impact of LearningML Software

Pablo Dúo-Terrón¹

¹Faculty of Education, Economics, and Technology of Ceuta., University of Granada, Granada, Spain | ²Advisor National Institute of Educational Technologies and Teacher Training, Ministry of Education, Vocational Training and Sports, Madrid, Spain | ³Rey Juan Carlos University, Madrid, Spain

Correspondence: Pablo Dúo-Terrón (pablduo@ugr.es)

Received: 22 October 2025 | **Revised:** 28 January 2026 | **Accepted:** 30 January 2026

Keywords: artificial intelligence | computer software | education | literacy | machine learning

ABSTRACT

Creating with artificial intelligence (AI) is fundamental to AI literacy through effective teaching methods and programmes. The aim is to suggest strategies for AI literacy education using LearningML software, based on machine learning, which allows users to create artificial intelligence models to recognise text and images without the need for programming knowledge. The study method is based on a systematic review of different databases that have integrated LearningML since 2020, their authors, countries, affiliations, keywords, associated resources, objectives, study methods, and conclusions, in order to determine the impact of the LearningML tool for integrating and developing AI literacy in teachers, students, and any user. The results were 48 documents that position LearningML software as a resource that can be integrated into curricula to promote AI literacy from primary education (K-8) to university, and even for any citizen. The main conclusions position this software in STEM fields, such as medicine, which recommend this software for understanding the fundamentals of AI. This tool helps address the challenge of preparing citizens for the future and making decisions about the use of AI.

1 | Introduction

The emergence of artificial intelligence (AI), for the general public and the educational field in particular, will disrupt many areas of everyday life [1]. In the educational field, most AI-based technological resources are focused on their use as intelligent assistants [2]. This use generates a lack of knowledge in the world of research about how it will affect the neurological, cognitive and emotional development of schoolchildren in the future or the effect it may have on skills such as creativity, curiosity, critical thinking or problem-solving abilities [3]. For this reason, there is an urgent need for AI literacy to develop essential skills for understanding, critically using and ethically applying AI, which is as fundamental as learning to read, write or do mathematics so that teachers and students understand how it works [4]. The new European digital competence framework (DigComp 3.0) has undergone a conceptual redesign aimed at integrating AI into schools so that teachers

understand, at least at a basic level, the logic behind how AI works, its limitations, biases, and side effects [5].

These tools in the teaching-learning process require innovation that goes beyond the educational framework, starting with AI literacy plans to achieve sustainable development goals [6]. AI literacy includes understanding how AI technologies work and how they are trained with data [7]. Training students for careers demanded by the digital society requires a clear understanding of the principles and practices of computer systems [8]. This poses a challenge in countering these threats due to the lack of training among teachers [9] that encourages thinking and learning about machine learning (ML) [10].

Due to the lack of research and evidence on AI teaching and learning in education [11, 12], this research focuses on the systematic review of the scientific production of the LearningML tool, which serves to educate and create AI models

This is an open access article under the terms of the [Creative Commons Attribution](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/) License, which permits use, distribution and reproduction in any medium, provided the original work is properly cited.

© 2026 The Author(s). *Computer Applications in Engineering Education* published by Wiley Periodicals LLC.

from an early age in an ethical and responsible manner [31] with the aim of improving this emerging field.

1.1 | AI and ML in Education

The adoption of AI in society and various labor sectors is evident [14]. This technology has emerged as one of the most transformative technologies of our time, influencing the field of education as well [15]. In 1955, McCarthy et al. [16] defined AI as the science and engineering of creating intelligent machines. Today, AI is understood as the ability of machines to use algorithms, learn from data, and apply that learning to decision-making processes, much like humans do [17].

AI is present and integral to our lives, changing the way schools, universities, and educational institutions operate and the way our children learn [18]. Education systems require proactive curricula that prepare students to be responsible users and co-creators of AI [18]. Computational thinking (CT) plays a crucial role in developing digital competence and critical thinking in AI literacy [19]. This forces teachers to develop technopedagogical skills to promote the ethical and reflective use of these tools among their students [20, 21]. It also allows for the identification of biases associated with high-risk AI systems [85].

AI requires computer systems to continuously adjust and improve data as it accumulates [22]. ML has an important role in computer science education [23] and is defined by Cruz et al. [24] as the set of algorithms and techniques used to build prediction and classification models from known data sets. Supervised ML, one of the most successful techniques, is based on models that receive a set of previously labeled or classified data as input [25]. The algorithm then adjusts the parameters of a model to learn patterns from this data [26]. Thanks to this learning process, the model can classify not only the input data but also new data whose classification was previously unknown.

Years ago, teaching these ML fundamentals, concepts, and techniques was common only in higher education institutions [63]. However, integrating CT into primary and secondary school curricula has become essential to solving problems with basic ML techniques and navigating a technology-driven world [27]. This has led to the development of adaptive learning tools that help students and non-expert users perform simple ML tasks via a visual interface [28, 29]. This learning process involves creating AI models with ML, enabling learners to understand and address ethical issues, thereby fostering AI literacy [11]. Consequently, active learning and ethical integration engage students effectively in learning how to create and critique AI artifacts [30].

1.2 | The LearningML Software

The use of AI by students, as well as the importance of ML knowledge from K-12 levels, creates a need to explore AI models with educational tools and resources, such as LearningML, from a constructive and creative point of view. LearningML is a free platform created in 2020 that is oriented toward supervised ML. Supervised ML is one of the most

effective AI techniques that supports most applications employing these systems [31]. Currently, an average of 700 students use it daily in schools and institutes throughout Spain [3]. This ML learning tool allows students and users to manage the types of data they enter [32]. Curating datasets and modifying one or more factors while observing ML model performance can help show which features are most relevant for classification [33].

LearningML [34] presents these features from various approaches and perspectives. From a pedagogical point of view, users can create AI models based on text, images, and numbers without prior programming knowledge. The generated AI models can be used for more complex projects involving visual programming blocks using programs such as Scratch or Snap! [35]. The advanced option allows users to observe black box or neural networks (Figure 1). These networks excel at supervised learning tasks, such as classification, but lack interpretability and the ability to explain how they make decisions [36].

Ethically, it is free software that does not require user registration (Figure 2). Completed projects can be downloaded to a computer as a “json” file and uploaded again. Thus, it complies with the data protection requirements for children under the age of 16 as established by [37] Regulation (EU) 2016/679 of the European Parliament, including when users enter emails and images, which are considered personal data. This platform does not have servers to host the data and information used by users and students to train models [38].

From an inclusive point of view, this platform can be downloaded and used on Windows, Linux, and MacOS devices without an Internet connection. This allows educational centers and users in areas with poor or no connection to work with it, ensuring universal access and adapting to regulations in different countries. It also allows for the integration of screen use by minors in environments without an internet connection.

According to data provided by LearningML, the number of users and time of use of the LearningML software has increased since May 2022, when records became available. Thus, during this time, the number of users amounts to 174,620 visits worldwide (Figure 3). In 2022, there were 10,369 visits; in 2023, there were 68,234; and in 2024, there were 96,017.

1.3 | Justification and Objectives

A lack of knowledge and skills in AI and ML limits the optimal implementation of these technologies in education [39]. While AI can bring many benefits, it can also negatively affect students [40]. For instance, exposure to AI algorithms that perpetuate biases may cause minors to internalize and perpetuate those biases [41]. Additionally, insufficient studies have examined the impact of AI use on students [42, 43, 75]), nor have they investigated the potential future effects of AI consumption. LearningML is a resource intended to be integrated into curricula to foster AI literacy [19]. It aims to transform students into creators of AI models with ML, thereby influencing future decisions regarding the use of AI and promoting digital and equitable development in schools [87].

FIGURE 1 | LearningML black box.

FIGURE 2 | ML models with LearningML and Scratch.

Following the methodological guidelines proposed by Kitchenham and Charters [44] for conducting systematic reviews in software engineering, this study aims to thoroughly examine the educational potential of LearningML

software as a tool for promoting personalized, adaptive learning experiences. The goal is to suggest strategies for AI literacy education. To achieve this goal, the following specific objectives are proposed:

FIGURE 3 | Record of LearningML user visits worldwide.

1. Provide a framework of scientific papers including LearningML software, updated with the main authors, countries, and affiliations.
2. Identify the study objectives and methods that include LearningML.
3. Extract keywords and associated resources from scientific literature highlighting LearningML.
4. Determine the main findings of papers referencing the LearningML resource.

2 | Method

This study employs a descriptive and quantitative systematic review based on the considerations of García-Peñalvo [45]. The aim is to identify what is known and unknown about the LearningML software for AI literacy. First, an analytical method was used to analyze and quantify the obtained data, which plays a significant role in this field of research [46]. This method was employed to classify and identify the evolution and scientific production of LearningML software in various databases. This approach enables search, registration, and prediction actions in scientific literature [47].

2.1 | Procedure and Data Analysis

The study followed a meticulous, multi-stage process to minimize biases in the data analysis [48]. The PRISMA protocol

(Figure 4) was used, as it is one of the most appropriate tools for selecting and filtering publication quality [49], with inclusion and exclusion criteria for the variables showing the obtained results [50]. Articles were searched for in all fields by entering the term “LearningML” in various high-impact international open-access databases such as Web of Science (WoS) ($n = 8$), Scopus ($n = 127$), ProQuest ($n = 66$) and CrossRef ($n = 3$). In addition, searches were conducted in databases specialising in education, such as ERIC ($n = 199$) and Erihplus ($n = 33$), as well as in Ibero-American publications on education sciences, such as Dialnet ($n = 4$) and Latindex ($n = 16$). This was complemented by the Mendeley bibliographic management database ($n = 5$) to detect additional literature from references and duplicates. A total of 461 articles were found in these databases. In addition, additional records were extracted independently from the official LearningML website, with reliability among evaluators, because it contains scientific articles and documents ($n = 8$) that offer functionalities on the software to enrich the systematic review of this study. This combination was selected to maximise the coverage of relevant studies, minimise language/country bias, and ensure the traceability and replicability of the search process.

During the screening phase, we excluded records outside the 2020–2024 period to cover five full years ($n = 32$), articles without abstracts or authors ($n = 6$), and articles with restricted or paid access ($n = 5$).

In the eligibility phase, 357 articles were excluded for the following reasons: the term “Learning ML” in the document did not correspond to the study software (292 articles excluded); the

FIGURE 4 | PRISMA protocol.

term “LearningML” was only present in the references section (47 articles excluded); documents that corresponded only to educational experiences (8 articles excluded); and articles that did not refer to the specific study software (112 articles excluded). Finally, duplicate records were found ($n = 21$). After the identification, exclusion, and eligibility phase, 48 articles were included in the systematic review of this study.

3 | Results

3.1 | Results Associated With the First Objective of the Study: Provide a Framework of Scientific Papers Including the LearningML Software, Along With the Main Authors, Countries, and Affiliations

LearningML is present in 48 scientific papers over the 5 years analyzed, which are detailed chronologically in Table 1. The presence of this software in scientific publications has increased since 2020 ($n = 1$) when the first article was published. Since then, the presence of LearningML has increased, with seven articles in 2021, 10 in 2022, 14 in 2023, and 16 in 2024.

A total of 119 authors from 18 different countries were found in the 48 analyzed papers (Figure 5). Spain and the United States had the most authors ($n = 28$). Sanusi-Temitayo, I. is the most influential author, citing LearningML in seven of his articles. Followed by researchers Dúo-Terrón, P., Robles-Martínez, G. and Rodríguez-García, J. D. with six contributions.

A total of 53 universities or institutions are present in the analyzed articles. The INTEF, Rey Juan Carlos University,

University of Eastern Finland, and University of Granada stand out with six contributions each. Table 2 shows institutions with at least four contributions.

3.2 | Results Associated With the Second Objective of the Study: To Identify the Study Objectives and Methods That Refer to or Include LearningML

In terms of study methods and objectives, we found 21 papers based on systematic reviews, four of which were conference contributions.

The reviews that cite LearningML have different objectives, such as reviewing design tools and AI integration techniques [10]; generative AI production in education [75]; and chatbots in the educational sector [57]. The reviews also aim to study how ML is used in primary and secondary education [53] and K-12 teaching and learning [53], as well as to understand ML through visual programming block tools [69]. The studies also aim to identify visual tools for developing custom ML applications and concepts in the context of K-12 education and practices ([54] a, 2021b). The literature on AI literacy was also identified [6, 11, 19]. Investigate pedagogical tools for AI literacy in K-12 settings [72] and in secondary school [59]. Learn about the evolution of AI in education [78] and in grades K-12 [55, 71]. Analyze AI teaching trends in the K-12 education system [43]. Find out the approach to using AI and ML in K-12 teaching and learning [12]. Analyze programs and projects implemented to improve education

TABLE 1 | Bibliographic matrix.

Articles	References
LearningML: A tool to foster computational thinking skills through practical artificial intelligence projects	Rodríguez-García et al. [31]
Bringing machine learning closer to non-experts: proposal of a user-friendly machine learning tool in the healthcare domain	Vázquez-Ingelmo et al. [51]
Conceptualizing AI literacy: An exploratory review	Ng et al. [11]
Evaluation of an online intervention to teach artificial intelligence with LearningML to 10-16-Year-Old Students	Rodríguez-García et al. [38]
Implementing functionality in LearningML	Merchán et al. [52]
Introducing artificial intelligence fundamentals with LearningML: Artificial Intelligence made easy	Rodríguez-García et al. [13]
Survey of resources for introducing machine learning in K-12 Context	Sanusi et al. [53]
Visual tools for teaching machine learning in K-12: A ten-year systematic mapping	Gresse Von Wangenheim et al. [54]
A literature review of AI education for K-12	Li-Li [55]
A proposal for performance-based assessment of the learning of machine learning concepts and practices in K-12	Gresse Von Wangenheim et al. [56]
Artificial intelligence in African Schools: Towards a contextualized approach	Ogbebor et al. [43]
Artificial intelligence literacy in higher and adult education: A scoping literature review	Laupichler et al. [19]
Chatbots in education. A systematic review of the science literature	Moreno-Guerrero et al. [57]
Exploring algorithmic liter exploring algorithmic literacy for college students: An E acy for College Students: An Educator's Roadmap	Gardner [58]
Findings on teaching machine learning in high school: A ten-year systematic literature review	Martins & Gresse Von Wangenheim [59]
Implementation of functionalities in LearningML: Audio recognition	Del Hoyo et al. [60]
Implementation of functionalities in LearningML: Recognition of (Datasets)	Rueda et al. [61]
Artificial intelligence as an educational resource during preservice teacher training	Ayuso & Gutierrez [84]
A review of digital learning environments for teaching natural language processing in K-12 education	Tian & Boyer [62]
A systematic review of teaching and learning machine learning in K-12 education	Sanusi et al. [63]
AI + ethics curricula for middle school youth: lessons learned from three project-based curricula	Williams et al. [30]
Analysis of scratch software in scientific production for 20 years: Programming in Education to Develop Computational Thinking and STEAM Disciplines	Dúo-Terrón [35]
Artificial Intelligence teaching and learning in K-12 from 2019 to 2022: A systematic literature review	Rizvi et al. [12]
Designing Game-Based Learning for High School Artificial Intelligence Education	Leitner et al. [64]
DoodleIt: A novel tool and approach for teaching how CNNs perform image recognition	Mahipal et al. [65]
Effects of voice assistant creation using different learning approaches on performance of computational thinking	Hsu et al. [66]
Artificial intelligence and machine learning as an educational resource from the perspective of teachers at different non-university educational stages	Dúo-Terrón et al. [9]
Intelligent design techniques towards implicit and explicit learning: a systematic review	Alqarni et al. [10]
Introduction to artificial intelligence from the mathematics classroom	Molina-Ayuso [67]
Learning machine learning with young children: exploring informal settings in an African context	Sanusi et al. [68]
Learning tools using block-based programming for AI Education	Fleger et al. [69]
Teaching machine learning in K-12 using robotics	Karalekas et al. [70]
A systematic review of the evaluation in K-12 artificial intelligence education from 2013 to 2022	Kim & Kwon [71]

(Continues)

TABLE 1 | (Continued)

Articles	References
AI literacy curriculum and its relation to children's perceptions of robots and attitudes towards engineering and science: An intervention study in early childhood education	Su & Yang [41]
Artificial intelligence (AI) learning tools in K-12 education: A scoping review	Yim & Su [72]
Assessing the Effectiveness of Textual Recommendations in KoopaML: A Comparative Study on Non-Expert Users' ML Pipeline Development	Antúnez-Muiños et al. [28]
ChemAIstry: A Novel Software Tool for Teaching Model Training in K-8 Education	Martin et al. [73]
The study of the application of an artificial intelligence workshop applied to sixth-grade children: artificial intelligence for children	Enríquez-Ramírez et al. [74]
Generative artificial intelligence: Educational reflections from an analysis of scientific production	Dúo-Terrón [75]
Global initiatives and challenges in integrating artificial intelligence literacy in elementary education: Mapping policies and empirical literature	Yeter et al. [6]
Innovative pathways: Artificial Intelligence as an Educational Catalyst in Programming and Computer Science Student Paper	Šaranović [76]
Integrating artificial intelligence and computational thinking in educational contexts: A systematic review of instructional design and student learning outcomes	Weng et al. [77]
Artificial Intelligence in Schools: A Systematic Review (2019–2023)	Bustamante & Camacho [78]
Machine Learning as a Methodological Resource in the Classroom	López-Belmonte et al. [79]
Machine Learning como recurso educativo en 4° de Primaria	Dúo-Terrón et al. [80]
AI MyData: Fostering Middle School Students' Engagement with Machine Learning through an Ethics-Infused AI Curriculum	Sanusi et al. [81]
OptiDot: An optical interface for children to explore dot product and AI recommendation	Zhou et al. [82]
Scratch-NB: A scratch extension for introducing K-12 learners to supervised machine learning	Quiroz & Gutierrez [83]

through AI [76]. Learn about tools and instructional designs for integrating AI and CT in educational contexts [77]. Study learning environments for teaching natural language processing in K-12 education [62].

Additionally, 11 research papers were found that use experiential learning to improve CT alongside AI application capabilities [66] and introduce AI and ML concepts in secondary classrooms [67]. Additionally, there are four works with exploratory approaches to determine how students learn and develop their understanding of ML-based technologies in playful and informal settings [68]. Examine students' perceptions of robots and their attitudes toward engineering and science [41]. Introduce the OptiDot interface to help students learn the fundamentals of numerous AI algorithms and recommendations through embodied learning experiences [82]. Describe a curriculum called AI MyData that teaches elements of ML and data science with an ethical orientation [81]. Present a study based on the comparative method of the KoopaML platform, which allows users with limited AI knowledge to build ML channels. The sample consisted of two groups of physicians inexperienced in AI who attempted to integrate ML algorithms into their clinical practice [28]. A mixed-methods approach ($n = 1$) describes how virtual training aimed at expanding AI knowledge was designed and developed [84]. A descriptive and comparative quantitative study ($n = 1$) was conducted to identify the impact of ML with LearningML on teachers [9].

A qualitative study ($n = 1$) aimed to explore how young children learn and develop an understanding of ML-based technologies in playful, informal settings [68]. Finally, a mixed-methods approach ($n = 1$) was used to learn about high school students' knowledge of and perceptions about AI before and after an AI workshop [30].

Finally, there are several contributions ($n = 16$) that present experiential tools and methods. These articles are distributed in conference proceedings ($n = 6$) and relate to CT and robotics in education, as discussed in a webinar by Rodríguez-García et al. [13] and in a study by Dúo-Terrón et al. [80] on teaching AI fundamentals through LearningML in the fourth grade of primary school. Other contributions include a pilot study introducing high school students to AI, ML and data science in an after-school programme [65]; a proposal for a user-friendly ML tool focusing on providing a positive user experience for clinicians [51]; and the presentation of interactive software tools such as ChemAIstry for children, which demonstrate ML training and classification of the trained model when classifying new objects [73]. There is also the presentation of interactive software tools for children, such as ChemAIstry, which demonstrate ML training and the classification of trained models when classifying new objects (Martín et al., 2024). There is also a study of an extension to the Scratch programming language called Scratch-NB, which provides K-8 students with the fundamental tools to develop a Naive Bayes classifier [83].

FIGURE 5 | Origin of authors' affiliations.

TABLE 2 | Article contributions by affiliation.

Affiliations	Articles
INTEF, Spain	6
Rey Juan Carlos University, Spain	6
University of the East, Finland	6
University of Granada, Spain	6
Faculty of Education, University of Hong Kong	4
University of Technology, Skellefteå, Sweden	4

In relation to the final degree projects ($n = 3$), they describe the implementation of new LearningML functionalities [52, 60, 61]. On the one hand, there are presentations of two platforms that employ AI: DoodleIt, which performs sketch recognition and provides an extracurricular curriculum for its use [64]; and the LearningML platform, which is aimed at supervised ML [31]. The two book chapters focus on analysing and evaluating students' understanding of and knowledge acquisition about AI [74], as well as learning through ML and Sustainable Development Goal no. 11 [79]. The bibliometric study ($n = 1$) analyses Scratch software [35]; the doctoral thesis ($n = 1$) examines the components of knowledge, coping behaviours, and pedagogical considerations to assist teaching staff in imparting algorithmic literacy to university students [58]; and the descriptive article ($n = 1$) provides insight into ML-based robotic kits [70].

3.3 | In Relation to the Third Objective of the Study: Extracting Keywords and Associated Resources From Scientific Publications That Refer to Learningml

A total of 174 keywords were found in the 48 analysed articles. Of these, 56 terms were repeated. Table 3 shows the terms that were repeated the most frequently (> 7), together with their associations in cases where the keyword was made up of two or more terms.

Of the 83 programmes associated with LearningML and identified during the analysis (Figure 6), 35 highlight Scratch, a software based on visual programming blocks. Other resources include ML for Kids ($n = 21$) and Google's Teachable Machine ($n = 19$).

3.4 | In Relation to the Fourth Objective of the Study: To Identify the Key Findings and Limitations of Documents Referencing the LearningML Resource

The main reviews of LearningML state that this software focuses on the learning, operation and basic concepts of AI [81] and is intended to support learning rather than to impart programming knowledge [76]. It is a platform that does not require registration and is suitable for teaching ML as an educational resource in the teaching and learning process at different non-university educational levels for children aged 10 to 16 ([30, 38, 59, 84]). It has a user-friendly visual interface that explains complex algorithms without going into technical detail [12, 51, 54].

TABLE 3 | Key words highlighted in articles with the presence of LearningML.

Terms	Total	Term Associations
IA	22	---
ML	19	---
Students	17	Students K-12 (15) y Students K-8 (2).
Education	11	Education (4), AI Education (2), Primary Education (1), Quality Education (1), Early Childhood Education (1), Computer Science in Education (2).
Learning	11	Learning (1), Implicit Learning (1), Learning Environments (1), Experiential Learning (1), Learner Behaviour in Learning (1), AI Learning (1), Game-based Learning (1), Learning Environment (1), Learning Outcomes (1), Online Learning (1), Learning Tools (1).
Teaching	9	Teaching AI (3), Higher teaching (1), Computer teaching (1), AI mediated teaching (1), intermediate level teaching (1), ML teaching (1) and Middle school teaching (1).
AI or digital literacy	7	---
Computational Thinking (CT)	7	---
Tool	7	AI tool (1), Conversational AI tool (1), Visual tool (1), Educational tools (1), Tools and resources (1), Learning tools (1), Software tools (1).
STEM	5	STEM (3) y STEAM (2).

FIGURE 6 | Resources associated with LearningML in the scientific literature.

It provides users with information about the ML processes of image and text recognition [53, 62, 74] and encourages thinking about and learning from supervised ML [10, 58, 65], with no need for prior knowledge [63, 70]. In addition, it enhances students' CT skills through practical AI projects [19, 28, 57, 77]. Using AI creation with LearningML enables active learning methodologies to be employed without the need for textbooks [79].

During the teaching and learning process, it enables students to remember, understand, apply, use, modify and create [54], as well as demystifying AI knowledge [72]. Cross-cutting STEAM projects based on AI can be developed, such as classifying mathematical problem statements, geometric figures, or stages

of prehistory [80]; [74]; Molina-Ayuso [67]), by integrating Scratch to utilise the trained model ([28, 30, 35, 43, 59, 69, 83]). This can help to identify why a machine makes erroneous predictions for humans, in other words, biases, as indicated by Dúo-Terrón's [75]. Research by Martin et al. [73] and Tian and Boyer [62] suggests that LearningML significantly improves the understanding of AI among 10–16-year-old participants, as demonstrated by pre- and post-test results.

4 | Discussion

According to the OECD [7], being creators in the context of AI literacy means having the ability to collaborate with AI systems

to generate original ideas, solve problems, and explore new perspectives. This enables students to guide and refine AI-generated outputs, ensuring that the resulting content is fair and appropriate while addressing ethical issues such as intellectual property rights and the responsible use of existing materials. In light of the necessity of teaching these fundamental AI concepts, ML has begun to be introduced in primary and secondary schools. Creating AI with LearningML enables non-expert users to carry out simple projects using a visual interface, as described by Antúnez-Muñoz et al. [28]. These skills are being integrated into educational curricula around the world, forcing teachers to develop this competence in their students, according to Monteyne et al. [20]. The following section discusses the results in relation to the study's objectives.

In relation to the first objective of the study to analyse the progression of LearningML software's scientific production, its main authors, countries and affiliations the results show that research on LearningML has increased over its first 5 years until 2024. This coincides with the emergence of AI in education and the need to integrate educational programmes that improve students' AI literacy from K-12 level by teaching them the basic fundamentals, the transversal application of AI in various contexts, and the ability to evaluate and create, as well as consider the ethical implications of AI [41, 81].

Spain and the USA lead in terms of affiliations and countries with the most articles referencing LearningML software. With the exception of Australia, all other continents are represented by articles citing LearningML. Spain stands out with 28 authors and the USA with 22, although the most prominent author is the Finnish researcher Sanusi, I. ($n = 7$).

According to Li-Li [55] and Molina-Ayuso [67], this diversity of productions around the world arises from the important need in education today to seek new methodological approaches to the teaching and learning process that prepare people to be responsible creators of AI. This emphasises the need for programmes such as LearningML. This prepares learners to be wiser consumers of AI in the future [82].

Addressing the second objective of the study, to identify the types of documents and study methods that exist on LearningML, the results corroborate the lack of knowledge and practical skills among educators in AI and ML. This limits the optimal implementation of these technologies in education, as indicated in the study by Forero-Corba & Negre-Bennasar [39]. This is because the majority of studies are systematic reviews of the scientific literature, as pointed out by Bustamante and Camacho [78]. However, LearningML appears as a cited tool in studies reviewing AI literacy in K-12 settings [11, 19, 72], and in studies reviewing ML teaching-learning tools in education [54, 59]. According to the [85] Regulation (EU) 2024/1689, the European Commission [17] and UNESCO [18, 86], these axes, where LearningML software appears, are the priority lines of action to be implemented in AI curricula. Provided it is adapted to the needs and abilities of students at each stage of their education, integrating AI concepts into educational activities that foster curiosity, creativity, and critical thinking, as outlined by the OECD [7], is beneficial.

According to the Office C report [3], research that has implemented ML programmes shows that learning ML and AI has an impact on students' future employment, not only in

academia, but in other sectors too. In line with this, the results of this research found two articles from the healthcare field: the studies by Antúnez-Muñoz et al. [28] and Vázquez-Ingelmo et al. [51]. These studies refer to the challenges that doctors may face when trying to integrate ML algorithms into their clinical practice using specific AI literacy programmes in the medical field. One example is KoopaML, which supports medical professionals in harnessing the power of AI. However, they suggest that educational modules using software such as LearningML should be included first, in order to make ML concepts more accessible and ensure that users develop a solid foundation in AI.

Regarding the third research objective of extracting keywords and associated resources from scientific literature including LearningML, it is notable that papers mentioning LearningML software prominently feature keywords such as CT, teaching and learning AI and ML in K-8 and K-12 environments for AI literacy, and using it as a tool for conducting STEM projects. Therefore, these keywords suggest that the minimum age for introducing ML is K-8, as highlighted in the studies by Martin et al. [73] and Quiroz and Gutiérrez (2024), in which students observe how the trained model classifies new objects, either without programming or by combining it with visual programming blocks.

In line with the study by Weng et al. [77], students develop an understanding of the various elements associated with AI and CT when they participate in ML activities, constructing meaning during the creation process. The authors argue that fostering AI/ML literacy could inspire more students to pursue STEM careers, offering them a robust foundation for higher education and their future careers, as suggested by the studies of Karalekas et al. [70] and Martins and Gresse Von Wangenheim [59].

LearningML is associated with other educational tools that can be used in schools to teach AI literacy. These tools are mainly linked to Scratch because ML projects can be extended using programming blocks, as pointed out in studies by Dúo-Terrón [35] and Molina-Ayuso [67]. There are also other similar programmes, such as ML for Kids and Teachable Machine. Unlike these, as pointed out in the studies by Ayuso and Gutiérrez [84] and [38], and [76], LearningML does not require registration or an email address. The database that trains users to create models must be downloaded to a local file. This ensures that images and personal data are hosted on unknown servers that do not belong to large companies such as Google or IBM, as reported by Mahipal et al. [65] and [83].

Finally, with regard to identifying the key references to the LearningML software in the documents, extracting the documents that mention the LearningML tool enables us to associate this resource with AI literacy, as no technical knowledge is required to learn ML, as highlighted by Alqarni et al. [10], Karalekas et al. [70], and Office C [3]. The authors concur with [66] study, which highlights the urgent need for the education sector to teach AI, in line with the rapid development of AI-related curricula for K-12 students. Consequently, AI can be democratised by employing open-source tools such as LearningML.

LearningML is associated with the need to understand the technology, pedagogy, and content knowledge involved in ML

teaching and learning, providing solid preparation for education and future careers, as indicated by Martins and Gresse von Wangenheim [59]. This resource, in line with UNESCO [4] recommendations on AI literacy, can go beyond understanding how these systems and their databases work. It questions how they behave, where and why bias appears, who decides what accuracy or balance means, and how AI systems reinforce stereotypes. In other words, critical literacy means recognising that AI is not neutral.

5 | Conclusions

The main conclusion of this study is that LearningML software has grown in prominence in scientific literature on AI and ML in education over the past 5 years, featuring in a total of 48 articles. Spain and the USA are the countries and authors that most frequently include LearningML in their articles. LearningML software appears most frequently in systematic reviews on various topics related to AI. Keywords associated with studies of this software refer to AI literacy, CT, ML, and AI teaching and learning in primary and secondary education, as well as STEM/STEAM projects.

Based on the references made in the various documents analysed, LearningML is proposed as a resource that addresses a current issue, not a future one, namely support for developing AI literacy. This is because the digital society already shapes the way we understand, experience and relate to the world. This software creates models with ML and can be used from the age of 8 up to university level, even with limited mathematical and computer science knowledge. Consequently, LearningML is a tool that facilitates the learning of AI concepts, which are sometimes too abstract, and can be integrated with visual block-based programming software such as Scratch. This knowledge prepares the educational community and other sectors to understand how AI applications can affect our lives, as well as the ethical issues surrounding AI technologies.

AI-based technologies offer significant support in education by facilitating more interactive learning environments tailored to individual needs. However, few education administrations integrate training aimed at encouraging users to engage critically with the responsible use of AI and acquire digital skills for its use and development. This training gap poses the risk that new generations will face disadvantages in meeting the challenges and opportunities of a society and economy increasingly defined by digital transformation. Given this problem, education and research policies should prioritise funding longitudinal studies to assess the long-term retention of AI literacy skills.

In the face of the challenges of responsible AI use, LearningML presents itself as a promising and secure platform for teaching and learning AI literacy at non-university and higher education levels, without the need for an internet connection. In the face of the challenges that educational policies and administrations face in promoting the responsible use of AI, LearningML emerges as a promising and secure platform for teaching AI literacy in non-university and higher education settings, eliminating the need for an internet connection. Furthermore, this study provides evidence of educational experiences that demonstrate how LearningML can be used in the classroom. These experiences can be replicated or serve as motivation for other

educational professionals to carry out cross-curricular projects that teach them how large language models are trained and encourage critical and responsible use.

This resource can be used in future research to evaluate educational interventions that measure the degree of AI literacy among teachers, students and other users. This will lay the foundations for teaching the fundamentals of AI and ML to young people and adults in a constructive and motivating way.

Author Contributions

Conceptualization: Pablo Dúo-Terrón, Juan David Rodríguez-García, and Gregorio Robles-Martínez. Methodology: Pablo Dúo-Terrón and A.J.M.G. Software: Antonio José Moreno-Guerrero. Formal analysis: Pablo Dúo-Terrón, Juan David Rodríguez-García, and Gregorio Robles-Martínez; Research: Pablo Dúo-Terrón, Juan David Rodríguez-García, Gregorio Robles-Martínez, and Antonio José Moreno-Guerrero. Data curation: Pablo Dúo-Terrón. Writing – preparation of the original draft: Pablo Dúo-Terrón and Juan David Rodríguez-García. Writing – review and editing: Pablo Dúo-Terrón, Juan David Rodríguez-García, Gregorio Robles-Martínez, and Antonio José Moreno-Guerrero; Visualization: Pablo Dúo-Terrón, Juan David Rodríguez-García, Gregorio Robles-Martínez, and Antonio José Moreno-Guerrero. Supervision: Juan David Rodríguez-García, Gregorio Robles-Martínez, and Antonio José Moreno-Guerrero.

Acknowledgments

Funding for open access charge: University of Granada/CBUA. The authors thank the Ministry of Science, Innovation and Universities for its collaboration through the AI4Software network (Red2022-134647-T).

Conflicts of Interest

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Data Availability Statement

The data used and analyzed in this study can be shared by the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

References

1. L. F. Fernández-Martínez, “La IA desde un punto de vista exotecnológico,” *Cuadernos Fronterizos* 58, no. 19 (2023): 50–54, <https://doi.org/10.20983/cuadfront.2023.58.13>.
2. K. Simbeck and Y. Kalf, “Understanding How Computers Learn: AI Literacy for Elementary School Learners.” in *Proceedings of Mensch Und Computer 2024*, eds. A. Maedche, M. Beigl, K. Gerling, and S. Mayer, (2024), 375–380. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3670653.3677511>.
3. C. Oficina. 2024. *Inteligencia artificial y educación, Retos y oportunidades en España*. Oficina de ciencia y tecnología del congreso de los diputados. <https://doi.org/10.57952/hqct-6d69>.
4. UNESCO., *AI and the Future of Education: Disruptions, Dilemmas and Directions* (UNESCO, 2025). <https://doi.org/10.54675/KECK1261>.
5. J. Cosgrove and R. Cachia. 2025. *DigComp 3.0: European Digital Competence Framework - Fifth Edition*. Publications Office of the European Union. <https://doi.org/10.2760/0001149>.
6. I. H. Yeter, W. Yang, and J. B. Sturgess, “Global Initiatives and Challenges in Integrating Artificial Intelligence Literacy in Elementary Education: Mapping Policies and Empirical Literature,” *Future in Educational Research* 2, no. 4 (2024): 382–402, <https://doi.org/10.1002/fer3.59>.

7. OECD., Empowering Learners for the Age of AI: An AI Literacy Framework for Primary and Secondary Education (Review draft) (OECD, 2025). <https://ailiteracyframework.org>.
8. S. C. Kong and H. Abelson, *Computational Thinking Education in K-12: Artificial Intelligence Literacy and Physical Computing* (The MIT Press, 2022).
9. P. Dúo-Terrón, A. J. Moreno-Guerrero, J. López-Belmonte, and J. A. Marín-Marín, “Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning as an Educational Resource From the Perspective of Teachers at Different Non-University educational Stages,” *Revista interuniversitaria de investigación en tecnología educativa* 15 (2023): 58–78, <https://doi.org/10.6018/riite.579611>.
10. F. Alqarni, O. Rana, and C. Perera, “Intelligent Design Techniques Towards Implicit and Explicit Learning: A Systematic Review,” *ORCA* (2023): 1–27, <https://orca.cardiff.ac.uk/id/eprint/163589>.
11. D. T. K. Ng, J. K. L. Leung, S. K. W. Chu, and M. S. Qiao, “Conceptualizing AI Literacy: An Exploratory Review,” *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence* 2 (2021): 100041, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2021.100041>.
12. S. Rizvi, J. Waite, and S. Sentance, “Artificial Intelligence Teaching and Learning in K-12 From 2019 to 2022: A Systematic Literature Review,” *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence* 4 (2023): 100145, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2023.100145>.
13. J. D. Rodríguez-García, J. Moreno-León, M. Román-González, and G. Robles, “Introducing Artificial Intelligence Fundamentals With LearningML: Artificial Intelligence made easy.” in *Eighth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality*, eds. F. J. García-Peñalvo and A. García-Holgado, (2021a), 18–20. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3434780.3436705>.
14. INTEF. Instituto nacional de tecnologías educativas y de formación del profesorado. *Guía sobre es uso de la Inteligencia Artificial en el ámbito educativo*. (Ministerio de educación, formación profesional y deportes, 2024). https://code.intef.es/wp-content/uploads/2024/07/Gu%C3%ADa-sobre-el-uso-de-la-IA-en-el-%C3%A1mbito-educativo-INTEF_2024.pdf.
15. J. McCarthy, M. L. Minsky, N. Rochester, and C. E. Shannon, “A Proposal for the Dartmouth Summer Research Project on Artificial Intelligence, August 31, 1955,” *AI Magazine* 27, no. 4 (2006): 12, <https://doi.org/10.1609/aimag.v27i4.1904>.
16. L. Rouhiainen, *Inteligencia Artificial. 101 cosas que debes saber hoy sobre nuestro futuro* (Editorial Alienta, 2018).
17. European Commission. Directorate General for Education, Youth, Sport and Culture., *Ethical Guidelines on the Use of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Data in Teaching and Learning for Educators* (Publications Office, 2022). <https://doi.org/10.2766/153756>.
18. UNESCO., *AI Competency Framework for Teachers* (UNESCO, 2024a). <https://doi.org/10.54675/ZJTE2084>.
19. M. C. Laupichler, A. Aster, J. Schirch, and T. Raupach, “Artificial Intelligence Literacy in Higher and Adult Education: A Scoping Literature Review,” *Computers and Education: Artificial Intelligence* 3 (2022): 100101, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeai.2022.100101>.
20. S. Monteyne, C. Struyve, N. Gesquière, et al., “Teachers’ Computational Thinking Content Knowledge: Development of a Measurement Instrument,” *Computers & Education* 225 (2025): 105181, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2024.105181>.
21. C. Muñoz-Martínez, V. Roger-Monzo, and F. Castelló-Sirvent, “Generative AI and Critical Thinking in Online Higher Education: Challenges and Opportunities,” *RIED-Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia* 28, no. 2 (2025): 233–273, <https://doi.org/10.5944/ried.28.2.43556>.
22. H. J. Poma-Cruz, “Machine Learning Models in Mining Geomechanics for the Efficient Control of Drilling,” *Revista de Investigaciones* 12, no. 1 (2023): 30–42, <https://doi.org/10.26788/ri.v12i1.4311>.
23. K. Zhu. *An Educational Approach to Machine Learning With Mobile Applications* [Doctoral thesis, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT), 2019]. MIT Libraries repository, <https://dspace.mit.edu/handle/1712.1/122989>.
24. E. Cruz, M. González, and J. C. Rangel, “Técnicas de machine learning aplicadas a la evaluación del rendimiento y a la predicción de la deserción de estudiantes universitarios, una revisión,” *Prisma Tecnológico* 13, no. 1 (2022): 77–87, <https://doi.org/10.33412/pri.v13.1.3039>.
25. V. Mirjalili and S. Raschka, *Python Machine Learning: Machine Learning and Deep Learning With Python, Scikit-Learn, and Tensorflow 2, Third Edition* (Packt>, 2020).
26. D. Serra, “Intervenciones experienciales en procesos de aprendizaje automático,” *Grafica* 13, no. 25 (2025): 179–185, <https://doi.org/10.5565/rev/grafica.325>.
27. M. H. Massaty, S. K. Fahrurrozi, and C. W. Budiyo, “The Role of AI in Fostering Computational Thinking and Self-Efficacy in Educational Settings: A Systematic Review,” *IJIE Indonesian Journal of Informatics Education* 8, no. 1 (2024): 49, <https://doi.org/10.20961/ijie.v8i1.89596>.
28. P. Antúnez-Muñoz, P. Pérez-Sánchez, A. Vázquez-Ingelmo, et al., “Assessing the Effectiveness of Textual Recommendations in KoopaML: A Comparative Study on Non-Expert Users’ ML Pipeline Development,” *International Journal on Semantic Web and Information Systems* 20, no. 1 (2024): 1–21, <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSWIS.340727>.
29. S. Priya, S. Bhadra, S. Chimalakonda, and A. S. M. Venigalla, “ML-Quest: A Game for Introducing Machine Learning Concepts to K-12 Students,” *Interactive learning environments* 32, no. 1 (2024): 229–244, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2022.2084115>.
30. R. Williams, S. Ali, N. Devasia, et al., “AI + Ethics Curricula for Middle School Youth: Lessons Learned From Three Project-Based Curricula,” *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* 33, no. 2 (2023): 325–383, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-022-00298-y>.
31. J. D. Rodríguez-García, J. Moreno-León, M. Román-González, and G. Robles, “LearningML: A Tool to Foster Computational Thinking Skills Through Practical Artificial Intelligence Projects,” *Revista de Educación a Distancia (RED)* 20, no. 63 (2020), <https://doi.org/10.6018/red.410121>.
32. O. Ayala-Cadena and I. Aguilar-Juárez, “La enseñanza de la programación mediante software educativo especializado y los agentes conversacionales,” *Interfases* 17, no. 017 (2023): 170–186, <https://doi.org/10.26439/interfases2023.n017.6337>.
33. T. L. Kurz, S. Jayasuriya, K. Swisher, J. Mativo, R. Pidaparti, and D. T. Robinson, “The Impact of Teachable Machine on Middle School Teachers’ Perceptions of Science Lessons After Professional Development,” *Education sciences* 14, no. 4 (2024): 417, <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14040417>.
34. LearningML. *LearningML - AI Made Easy*. (2020). <https://web.learningml.org/>.
35. P. Dúo-Terrón, “Analysis of Scratch Software in Scientific Production for 20 Years: Programming in Education to Develop Computational Thinking and STEAM Disciplines,” *Education sciences* 13, no. 4 (2023): 404, <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13040404>.
36. G. Ras, N. Xie, M. Van Gerven, and D. Doran, “Explainable Deep Learning: A Field Guide for the Uninitiated,” *Journal of artificial intelligence research* 73 (2022): 329–397, <https://doi.org/10.1613/jair.1.13200>.
37. Regulation (EU), “2016/679 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 27 April 2016 on the Protection of Natural Persons With Regard to the Processing of Personal Data and on the Free Movement of

- Such Data, and Repealing Directive 95/46/EC (General Data Protection Regulation),” *Official Journal of the European Union* L 119, May 4 (2016): 1–88, <http://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj>.
38. J. D. Rodríguez-García, J. Moreno-León, M. Román-González, and G. Robles. “Evaluation of an Online Intervention to Teach Artificial Intelligence With LearningML to 10-16-Year-Old Students,” In M. Sherriff, L. D. Merkle, P. Cutter, A. Monge, and J. Sheard (Eds.), *Proceedings of the 52nd ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education* (2021b), (pp. 177–183). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3408877.3432393>.
39. W. Forero-Corba and F. Negre-Bennasar, “Técnicas y aplicaciones del Machine Learning e Inteligencia Artificial en educación: Una revisión sistemática,” *RIED-Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia* 27, no. 1 (2023): 209–253, <https://doi.org/10.5944/ried.27.1.37491>.
40. C. Valls-Bautista, J. Holgado-García, L. Marqués-Molíias, and M. Usart-Rodríguez, *Transformació Digital de l'Educació a l'Era de la Intel·ligència Artificial: Una Revolució Imparable* (Dykinson, 2024). 1a ed. <https://doi.org/10.14679/3500>.
41. J. Su and W. Yang, “AI Literacy Curriculum and Its Relation to Children’s Perceptions of Robots and Attitudes Towards Engineering and Science: An Intervention Study in Early Childhood Education,” *Journal of Computer Assisted Learning* 40, no. 1 (2024): 241–253, <https://doi.org/10.1111/jcal.12867>.
42. J. Felix and L. Webb. *Use of Artificial Intelligence in Education Delivery and Assessment* (Parliamentary Office of Science and Technology, 2024). <https://doi.org/10.58248/PN712>.
43. S. S. Oyelere, I. T. Sanusi, F. J. Agbo, et al. (2022). “Artificial Intelligence in African Schools: Towards a Contextualized Approach,” In 2022 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON), 1577–1582. (2022). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON52537.2022.9766550>.
44. B. Kitchenham and S. Charters. *Guidelines for Performing Systematic Literature Reviews in Software Engineering*. Technical report, EBSE Technical Report EBSE-2007-01 (2007). https://legacyfiles.elsevier.com/promis_misc/525444systematicreviewsguide.pdf.
45. F. J. García-Peñalvo, “Desarrollo de estados de la cuestión robustos: Revisiones Sistemáticas de Literatura,” *Education in the Knowledge Society (EKS)* 23 (2022): e28600, <https://doi.org/10.14201/eks.28600>.
46. M. A. Martínez, M. J. Cobo, M. Herrera, and E. Herrera-Viedma, “Analyzing the Scientific Evolution of Social Work Using Science Mapping,” *Research on Social Work Practice* 25, no. 2 (2014): 257–277, <https://doi.org/10.1177/1049731514522101>.
47. J. E. Hirsch, “An Index to Quantify an Individual’s Scientific Research Output,” *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences* 102, no. 46 (2005): 16569–16572, <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.0507655102>.
48. E. Parra-González, A. Segura-Robles, M. R. Vicente-Bújez, and J. López-Belmonte, “Production Analysis and Scientific Mapping on Active Methodologies in Web of Science,” *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)* 15, no. 20 (2020): 71–86, <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v15i20.15619>.
49. S. Sánchez-Serrano, I. Pedraza-Navarro, and M. Donoso-González, “Cómo hacer una revisión sistemática siguiendo el protocolo PRISMA? Usos y estrategias fundamentales para su aplicación en el ámbito educativo a través de un caso práctico,” *Bordón. Revista de Pedagogía* 74, no. 3 (2022): 51–66, <https://doi.org/10.13042/Bordon.2022.95090>.
50. L. Shamseer, D. Moher, M. Clarke, et al., “Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Review and Meta-Analysis Protocols (PRISMA-P) 2015: Elaboration and Explanation,” *BMJ* 349 (2015): g7647, <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.g7647>.
51. A. Vázquez-Ingelmo, J. Alonso-Sánchez, A. García-Holgado, et al. “Bringing Machine Learning Closer to Non-Experts: Proposal of a User-friendly Machine Learning Tool in the Healthcare Domain,” In M. Alier, D. Fonseca (Eds.), *Ninth International Conference on Technological Ecosystems for Enhancing Multiculturality (TEEM’21)*, (2021), 324–329. <https://doi.org/10.1145/3486011.3486469>.
52. I. Merchan, G. Robles, and J. D. Rodríguez. *Implementación de funcionalidades en LearningML/Implementing Functionality in LearningML*. [Final Degree Project, Rey Juan Carlos University, 2021]. Rey Juan Carlos University repository <https://gysc.urjc.es/~grex/pfcs/2021-isaac-merchan/IsaacMerchan-ImplementacionFuncionalidadesEnLearningML.pdf>.
53. I. T. Sanusi, S. S. Oyelere, F. J. Agbo, and J. Suhonen (2021). “Survey of Resources for Introducing Machine Learning in K-12 Context,” In 2021 IEEE Frontiers in education conference (FIE), 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1109/FIE49875.2021.9637393>.
54. C. Gresse Von Wangenheim, J. C. R. Hauck, F. S. Pacheco, and M. F. Bertonceli Bueno, “Visual Tools for Teaching Machine Learning in K-12: A Ten-Year Systematic Mapping,” *Education and Information Technologies* 26, no. 5 (2021): 5733–5778, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10570-8>.
55. Li-Li, “A Literature Review of AI Education for K-12,” *Canadian Journal for new Scholars in Education* 13, no. 3 (2022): 114–121, <https://journalhosting.ualgry.ca/index.php/cjnse/article/view/76563>.
56. C. Gresse Von Wangenheim, N. D. C. Alves, M. F. Rauber, J. C. R. Hauck, and I. H. Yeter, “A Proposal for Performance-Based Assessment of the Learning of Machine Learning Concepts and Practices in K-12,” *Informatics in education* 21, no. 3 (2022): 479–500, <https://doi.org/10.15388/infedu.2022.18>.
57. A.-J. Moreno-Guerrero, J. A. Marín-Marín, P. Dúo-Terrón, and J. López-Belmonte, “Chatbots in Education. A Systematic Review of the Science Literature.” in *Artificial intelligence in higher education. A practical approach*, eds. P. Padmakar, S. Joshi, M. Elhoseny, and A. Omrane. (Taylor & Francis Group, 2022), 81–94.
58. S. Gardner. *Exploring Algorithmic Literacy for College Students: An e acy for College Students: An Educator’s Roadmap*. [Doctoral thesis, Loyola Marymount University, Los Angeles, 2022]. Loyola Marymount University repository <https://digitalcommons.lmu.edu/etd/1160>.
59. R. M. Martins and C. Gresse Von Wangenheim, “Findings on Teaching Machine Learning in High School: A Ten-Year Systematic Literature Review,” *Informatics in Education* 22, no. 3 (2022): 421–440, <https://doi.org/10.15388/infedu.2023.18>.
60. Á. Del Hoyo, G. Robles, and J. D. Rodríguez. *Implementación de funcionalidades en LearningML: Reconocimiento de audio* [Final Degree Project, Rey Juan Carlos University, 2022]. Rey Juan Carlos University repository <https://gysc.urjc.es/~grex/pfcs/2021-isaac-merchan/>.
61. I. Rueda, G. Robles, and J. D. Rodríguez. *Implementación de funcionalidades en LearningML: reconocimiento de conjuntos de datos* (Datasets) [Final Degree Project, Rey Juan Carlos University, 2022]. Rey Juan Carlos University Repository, <https://gysc.urjc.es/~grex/pfcs/2021-isaac-merchan/IsaacMerchan-ImplementacionFuncionalidadesEnLearningML.pdf>.
62. X. Tian and K. E. Boyer. *A Review of Digital Learning Environments for Teaching Natural Language Processing in K-12 Education* (Versión 1) (2023). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/ARXIV.2310.01603>.
63. I. T. Sanusi, S. S. Oyelere, H. Vartiainen, J. Suhonen, and M. Tukiainen, “A Systematic Review of Teaching and Learning Machine Learning in K-12 Education,” *Education and Information Technologies* 28, no. 5 (2023a): 5967–5997, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11416-7>.
64. M. Leitner, E. Greenwald, N. Wang, R. Montgomery, and C. Merchant, “Designing Game-Based Learning for High School Artificial Intelligence Education,” *International Journal of Artificial Intelligence in Education* 33 (2023): 384–398, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40593-022-00327-w>.
65. V. Mahipal, S. Ghosh, I. T. Sanusi, R. Ma, J. E. Gonzales, and F. G. Martin. “DoodleIt: A Novel Tool and Approach for Teaching How CNNs Perform Image Recognition,” In *Proceedings of the 54th ACM*

- Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V. 1 (SIGCSE 2023) (2023), (pp. 31–38). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3576123.3576127>.
66. T.-C. Hsu, C. Chang, and Y.-W. Lin, “Effects of Voice Assistant Creation Using Different Learning Approaches on Performance of Computational Thinking,” *Computers & Education* 192 (2023): 104657, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2022.104657>.
67. A. Molina-Ayuso, “Introduction to Artificial Intelligence From the Mathematics Classroom,” *Epsilon* 114 (2023): 99–111, <https://thales.cica.es/epsilon/node/5008>.
68. I. T. Sanusi, K. Sunday, S. S. Oyelere, J. Suhonen, H. Vartiainen, and M. Tukiainen, “Learning Machine Learning With Young Children: Exploring Informal Settings in an African Context,” *Computer Science Education* 34, no. 2 (2023b): 161–192, <https://doi.org/10.1080/08993408.2023.2175559>.
69. C. B. Fleger, Y. Amanuel, and J. Krugel (2023). “Learning Tools Using Block-Based Programming for AI Education,” In 2023 IEEE Global Engineering Education Conference (EDUCON) (pp.1–5). <https://doi.org/10.1109/EDUCON54358.2023.10125154>.
70. G. Karalekas, S. Vologianidis, and J. Kalomiros, “Teaching Machine Learning in K–12 Using Robotics,” *Education Sciences* 13, no. 1 (2023): 67, <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci13010067>.
71. K. Kim and K. Kwon, “A Systematic Review of the Evaluation in K-12 Artificial Intelligence Education From 2013 to 2022,” *Interactive Learning Environments* 33, no. 1 (2024): 103–131, <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2024.2335499>.
72. I. H. Y. Yim and J. Su, “Artificial Intelligence (AI) Learning Tools in K-12 Education: A Scoping Review,” *Journal of Computers in Education* 12 (2024): 93–131, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40692-023-00304-9>.
73. F. Martin, V. Mahipal, G. Jain, S. Ghosh, and I. T. Sanusi. “ChemAIstry: A Novel Software Tool for Teaching Model Training in K-8 Education,” In B. Stephenson, J. A. Stone, L. Battestilli, S. A. Rebersky, and L. Shoop (Eds.), SIGCSE 2024: Proceedings of the 55th ACM Technical Symposium on Computer Science Education V.1 (2024), (pp. 792–798). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626252.3630804>.
74. C. Enríquez-Ramírez, M. Raluy-Herrero, F. A. Elizalde-Canales, and A. D. López-Hernández, “El estudio de aplicación de taller de inteligencia artificial aplicada a niños de sexto de primaria: inteligencia artificial para niños.” in *RELEN. Educación Normal en Latinoamérica/ Normal Education in Latin America. 2023*, eds. N. B. Peña Ahumada and O. C. Aguilar Rascón, (iQuatro Editores, 2024), 97–111. <https://doi.org/10.46990/iQuatro.2024.08.5.8>.
75. P. Dúo-Terrón, “Generative Artificial Intelligence: Educational Reflections From an Analysis of Scientific Production,” *Journal of technology and science education* 14, no. 3 (2024): 756, <https://doi.org/10.3926/jotse.2680>.
76. M. Šaranović. “Innovative Pathways: Artificial Intelligence as an Educational Catalyst in Programming and Computer Science Student Paper,” In *2024 23rd International Symposium Infoteh-Jahorina (INFOTEH)*, (2024), 1–5. <https://doi.org/10.1109/INFOTEH60418.2024.10495960>.
77. X. Weng, H. Ye, Y. Dai, and O. Ng, “Integrating Artificial Intelligence and Computational Thinking in Educational Contexts: A Systematic Review of Instructional Design and Student Learning Outcomes,” *Journal of educational computing research* 62, no. 6 (2024): 1420–1450, <https://doi.org/10.1177/07356331241248686>.
78. R. Bustamante Bula and A. Camacho Bonilla, “Inteligencia artificial (IA) en las escuelas: una revisión sistemática (2019-2023),” *Enunciación* 29, no. 1 (2024): 62–82, <https://doi.org/10.14483/22486798.22039>.
79. J. López-Belmonte, P. Dúo-Terrón, J. A. Marín-Marín, and A. J. Moreno-Guerrero, “Machine Learning as a Methodological Resource in the Classroom.” in *Artificial Intelligence of Things for Achieving Sustainable Development Goals*, eds. S. Misra, K. Siakas, and G. Lampropoulos. Lecture Notes on Data Engineering and Communications Technologies, 2024. 192, 233–253. https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-53433-1_12.
80. P. Dúo-Terrón, Moreno-Guerrero, and S. Pozo-Sánchez, “Machine Learning como recurso educativo en 4° de Primaria.” in *Tecnología Educativa para una Sociedad Multimodal. Libro de actas EDUTEC'24*, eds. J. Cabero-Almenara, A. Palacios-Rodríguez, M. Montenegro-Rueda, and J. Fernández-Cerero (2024), 173–176. <https://edutec24.es/>.
81. I. T. Sanusi, F. Martin, R. Ma, et al., “AI MyData: Fostering Middle School Students’ Engagement With Machine Learning Through Aan Ethics-Infused AI Curriculum,” In A. J. Ko (Eds.), *ACM Transactions on Computing Education* 24, no. 4 (2024): 1–37, <https://doi.org/10.1145/3702242>.
82. X. Zhou, P. Xiong, Q. Xiao, and Z. Bai (2024). “OptiDot: An Optical Interface for Children to Explore Dot Product and AI Recommendation,” In F. Floyd and P. Kyburz (Eds.), CHI EA ‘24: Extended Abstracts of the CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (pp. 1–7). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3613905.3651040>.
83. P. Quiroz and F. J. Gutierrez. “Scratch-NB: A Scratch Extension for Introducing K-12 Learners to Supervised Machine Learning,” In B. Stephenson, J. A. Stone, L. Battestilli, S. A. Rebersky, and L. Shoop (Eds.), Proceedings of the 55th ACM Technical symposium on computer science education V. 1 (2024), (pp. 1077–1083). <https://doi.org/10.1145/3626252.3630920>.
84. D. Ayuso and P. Gutiérrez, “Artificial Intelligence as an Educational Resource During Preservice Teacher Training,” *RIED-Revista Iberoamericana de Educación a Distancia* 25, no. 2 (2022): 347–362, <https://doi.org/10.5944/ried.25.2.32332>.
85. Regulation (EU)., “2024/1689 of the European Parliament and of the Council of 13 June 2024 on Artificial Intelligence (Artificial Intelligence Act),” *Official Journal of the European Union*: 1–44, <https://data.europa.eu/eli/reg/2024/1689/oj>.
86. UNESCO., *AI Competency Framework for Students* (UNESCO, 2024b). <https://doi.org/10.54675/JKJB9835>.
87. Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología, Conocimiento e Innovación. *Política nacional de Inteligencia Artificial* (Gobierno de Chile, 2024). <https://www.minciencia.gob.cl/areas/inteligencia-artificial/politica-nacional-de-inteligencia-artificial/>.